

Interview Guide: Quality in Use of Dependability Evaluation Approach

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Demographics:

- Name:
- Role:
- Experience:

Effectiveness

- Does the application of the dependability measurement approach derive dependability requirements and measures?
- Is the usage of SLOs and SLIs for defining dependability characteristics and measures suitable to indicate dependability from a consumer-centric view?
- What problems did you have?
- Was it possible to explore the dynamic view of a transaction?

Efficiency and Satisfaction

- Is information explained and presented in a clear and understandable way?
- Is the usage of the dependability measurement approach efficient?
- Does it contribute to reduce complexity of observation?
- How satisfied are you with the approach?

Open Questions:

- What do you think is the most valuable factor of the procedure, and why?
- What do you think needs improvement, and why?